

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_e_Topo		
Created on:	4/15/2021 12:16:18 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	29.31	μm	
Size:	65531	digits	
Spacing:	0.4473	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x...filtered (λ_s 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_e_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/15/2021 12:16:18 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	16.43	μm	
Min:	-8.509	μm	
Max:	7.922	μm	
Size:	367326	digits	
Spacing:	0.04473	nm	
NM-points ratio:	10.72 % (964810 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_na...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/15/2021 12:16:18 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	16.43	μm	
Size:	367326	digits	
Spacing:	0.04473	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.768	μm	
Ssk	-0.9285		
Sku	5.866		
Sp	7.914	μm	
Sv	8.517	μm	
Sz	16.43	μm	
Sa	1.249	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.1263	%	
Smc	1.658	μm	
Sxp	4.699	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	20.73	μm	
Str	0.8132		
Std	62.00	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.4032		
Sdr	6.562	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.09447	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	1.752	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.09447	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	1.276	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	1.409	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.3434	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

- ISO 25178 8.
- Furrow 9.
- Texture direction 10.
- Texture isotropy 11.
- SSFA 12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	8.685	µm
Mean depth of furrows	1.536	µm
Mean density of furrows	3423	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	44.99	°
Second direction	63.51	°
Third direction	90.02	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	92.32	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

